

In What Manner Did the Bogotazo Enable the Manifestation of Anticlerical and Anti-Evangelical Ideas in Colombia?

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I. Introduction

When traveling throughout Colombia, one will invariably find a church with a public square in front in every town or city. Along the highways, there is always a statue of the Virgin Mary to pray to for the traveler's safety. The Primatial Cathedral of Bogotá occupies a central position alongside the Capitol, the Palace of Justice, and the Casa de Nariño, which attests to the historical relevance of the Catholic faith in the country. Colombia, long known as a state devoted to its Catholic principles, has been distinguished by its zeal for this Church. For this reason, other Christian religions appear to have been overshadowed and their history forgotten, while Catholic supremacy remains intact.

The purpose of this paper is not to refute the Catholic faith, but to analyze its impact and political relations within the country. Although the history could be traced at length, a decisive moment for the delimitation of this work is the Bogotazo—a series of disturbances triggered by the assassination of Jorge Eliécer Gaitán and the most significant manifestation of the bipartisan conflict—which is rife with gaps in knowledge given the unresolved nature of the events. This episode demonstrated the importance of religion in politics and how the two mutually reinforce one another, subsequently giving rise to anticlerical and anti-evangelical ideas. The interest of this monograph is therefore to unmask the incidences and consequences that religion had in relation to the Bogotazo.

This paper is intended to provide a general overview of the events that have marked the history of persecution in the country, as a topic of such breadth could only be addressed within the political and social sphere in this monograph. The methodology employed is the analytical-synthetic method, as diverse sources were analyzed and compared in order to briefly contextualize the little-known history of the Evangelical Church and subsequently establish its relationship—as well as that of the Catholic Church—with politics and the Bogotazo, thereby optimizing understanding in order to arrive at a reasoned and impartial response.

II. Terminology

Christianity is arguably the only religion established in every country, professing the teachings of Jesus and recognizing him as God and Messiah, as Bowen (2017) explains. This religion has divided into several branches over the centuries, either by following the teachings of the Bible or by distancing itself from them through tradition or other factors. The most important divisions mentioned in this work include Protestantism, which—as Semán and Viotti (2018) as well as Evans (2018) note—is an international movement applied to churches that originated from the Evangelical or Protestant Reformation of the sixteenth century, and for which these two terms are therefore interchangeable.

According to Evans (2018), the Presbyterian Church refers to reformed churches in English-speaking countries with an emphasis on education and progress, whose roots center on the work of John Knox, grounded in Calvinist theology. Finally, the Catholic Church terminologically refers to a 'Universal' church, though it has changed considerably from its precepts in the Ancient Catholic Church to become the Roman Catholic Apostolic Church, the most widely known worldwide given its affiliation with the Roman Empire.

A final term is Freemasonry, which Evans (2018) describes as a secret fraternal organization of men that emerged in Europe at the end of the seventeenth century, rejected in various countries due to supposed connections with occultism.

III. Historical Context of the Christian Church in Colombia

Beltrán (2004) and Ordoñez (1958) declare that the Protestant faith arrived in the national territories during the colonial period in the seventeenth century, specifically on the island of San Andrés through Anglican influence, but attempts to bring it to the continental territory were frustrated by the Inquisition.

Nevertheless, during Bolívar's time, Beltrán (2004) comments on the anti-Catholic thinking of the independence movement regarding Gran Colombia, which went so far as to request the support of Joseph Lancaster for an educational reform in the country. According to the Encyclopaedia Britannica, the Lancasterian system included the use of the Bible as a textbook, supporting the Lutheran religious idea of free inquiry and stimulating the development of critical thinking skills. However, attempts to introduce this system in 1822 failed due to the opposition of the Catholic Church, which controlled the educational system, leading to the obstruction of personal religious opinion, as noted by Beltrán (2004) and Abadía (2012).

Following independence, the nineteenth century saw the beginning of the struggle between Liberals and Conservatives in the country, with religion as a decisive battleground due to its influence over the masses. Liberals—tacitly associated with Evangelicals and adherents of Enlightenment ideals such as the separation of Church and State and the defense of critical reasoning, as Beltrán (2004) and Arboleda (2006) explain—would engage in a war against the Conservative Party. An example is President Tomás Cipriano de Mosquera, who switched from the Conservative to the Liberal side in 1854, supporting Protestant churches and the idea of the Church's subordination to the State. The Lerdo Law fulfilled this purpose by confiscating disused or 'dead hand' properties, many of them belonging to the Catholic Church, under the pretext of stimulating the market. These and other threats faced by the Church worldwide led to efforts by Pope Leo XIII to improve political relations through the Concordat of 1887. (Abadía, 2012)

In 1861, the Presbyterian Reverend Guillermo McLaren received a letter from a Supreme Court judge informing him that President Mosquera wished for more Protestant missionaries to arrive, and also offered him a chapel from a former Jesuit convent taken over by the Government under the Lerdo Law, demonstrating the president's support for freedom of belief and enabling the creation of the Central Presbyterian Church in Bogotá—the first Evangelical church in Colombia. (Arboleda, 2002)

Monsignor Canuto Restrepo, Bishop of Pasto, wrote in 1872 about these events:

The Liberal School System obeys a premeditated plan against the Church, part of the universal conspiracy of all liberal and Masonic governments in the world. (Abadía, 2012)

Abadía (2012) and Beltrán (2004) complement their theses regarding the Freemasons, the former stating that Evangelical missionaries were regarded as such, and the latter going further by maintaining that all Liberals and their affiliates were considered Freemasons, a fact proclaimed loudly from the pulpits by various priests.

Colombia has lacked the formation of a common identity due to its cultural diversity, making it difficult to find an equitable point for accepting differences. The Catholic Church took advantage of this division to recover its political power by employing rites, cults, saints, festivals, and superstitions as sources of identity and social cohesion—a practice Ordoñez (1958) characterizes as fanaticism. In this environment, the Church regained social and political power, with President Rafael Núñez as its great Conservative exponent and promoter of the Constitution's reform in 1886, which favored this religion by restricting freedom of worship, imposing confessional education, and influencing other areas of daily life.

Article 38. The Catholic, Apostolic, and Roman Religion is the religion of the Nation; the public authorities shall protect it and ensure that it is respected as an essential element of the social order. Article 41. Public education shall be organized and directed in accordance with the Catholic Religion. (Political Constitution of the Republic of Colombia, 1886)

In 1912, Rafael Uribe, a Colombian diplomat and military officer, wrote the essay 'On How Liberalism in Colombia Is Not a Sin,' designated as a forbidden book by the Vatican. In this essay, he argues that Liberals support Protestantism because of the freedom of conscience it proclaims. Its purpose is to demonstrate his concern about the persecution suffered by Liberals in the country and to offer a critique of the Catholic Church, sharply noting its lack of support for modernity. Uribe emphasizes that being Liberal is not the same as being anti-Catholic, although many believed otherwise due to the Church's allegations. (Uribe, 1912)

In 1920, socialist ideologies began to emerge in the country, and as some Liberal leaders had sympathies with these, Protestantism was tacitly linked with them, which in some sense inflamed the events of April 9, 1948—the Bogotazo. The 1930s were an important period for the Liberal Party during its hegemony, given the constitutional reform carried out in 1936. This reform is remembered as a revolutionary milestone, with some authors going so far as to label it a Soviet code (Botero, 2006), by virtue of its social emphasis, as it sought the well-being of workers by providing support to trade unions, permitting freedom of worship, and introducing other changes that exacerbated the bipartisan conflict. This dispute was fought to the death not by the leaders of the ideologies, but by citizens in many cases incapable of articulating their ideological position, driven by fear and tradition.

In response to the 1936 reform, several Catholic priests spoke out, with Monsignor Miguel Ángel Builes among its most radical opponents:

Now this sect (Protestantism) is cracking, collapsing, and disappearing to give way to Communism, which, directed and aided by Freemasonry, rises up against God and against Christ, against the Catholic Church and against religion, against the Christian social order and against the peace and tranquility of nations. (Builes, 1957)

IV. The Bogotazo

Many Colombians longed for a change from the government of President Mariano Ospina Pérez, a member of the Conservative Party, who maintained an autarchic system causing misery and social hysteria, while fear grew due to the Chulavita police and the Pájaros—the military backing of the Conservative Party. In this context, a leader 'of the people' was gaining ground ahead of the upcoming elections: Jorge Eliécer Gaitán. (Trejos, 2011)

The Pájaro was a radical figure sheltered by individuals entrenched in departmental politics, thus enjoying impunity and high monetary rewards. He was a hired assassin tasked with eliminating Liberals, who believed he was not committing crimes but defending God. It should be noted that the Pájaro had no education beyond primary school and was convinced to act through appeals to the defense of the sacred. He was contracted to carry out work at a price that varied depending on the victim—whether a citizen or a politician—with these selective killings planned in advance. Gómez (2014) employs the striking expression:

It operated in the style of the Ku Klux Klan, but a Creole version. (Gómez, 2014)

The author introduces the story of Abel, a presumed Pájaro in the departments of Nariño and Valle del Cauca during 'La Violencia.' Abel exerted pressure on Liberals who attended church, telling them they had no right to be there. He did not see the Liberal as a normal person, but as an adversary who in his heart denied God. Teresa, his wife, emphasizes that he never spoke of politics because he truly did not know what it consisted of. The differences between parties he could only associate with friendship or enmity with the Catholic Church.

On April 9, 1948, Gaitán was assassinated, bringing about unrest, protests, looting, the burning of the emblematic tramcar, and disturbances near the Palace of Justice demanding the resignation of President Ospina Pérez. This event gave rise to the period that would last more than ten years and be known as 'La Violencia'—the height of the armed confrontation between Liberals and Conservatives with the characteristics of a civil war. (Aleans, 2012)

Following the death of the Liberal caudillo—supported by popular sectors due to his critique of the oligarchy and his syndicalist backing—the crowd, in a state of panic and intoxication, headed toward the prison and freed inmates. The city seemed to replicate the disturbances that took place in France during the storming of the Bastille in 1789. Over the radio, the ringleaders of this national uprising called for the destruction of Catholic churches and religious houses, accusing them of harboring snipers ready to kill the people. As Rojas (2020) documents, the crowd in Bogotá destroyed the Archbishop's House, the Apostolic Nunciature, the Javeriana University's Women's Faculties, the convents of the Augustinian and Conceptionist nuns, the Church of the Hospicio, the parish house of La Veracruz, the Colegio San Bartolomé de la Merced, the offices of El Catolicismo, and the Instituto de la Salle, among others. The uprising, with its burnings and profanations, reached Barranquilla, where the Vincentian Fathers' convent and the Salesian school were occupied and the cathedral set on fire. Parish priests in departments such as Tolima were killed, and Javeriana missionaries in Magdalena were also shot and macheted. Rojas cites the Colombian bishops' pronouncement on the events of April 9th:

We could never have imagined that such an act, carried out on Colombian soil, would come to add itself to the multiple and notorious manifestations of the satanic hatred with which atheism and Communist barbarism have in other latitudes offended and persecuted,

by the most criminal means, the Catholic religion...with the attacks on the dignity and liberty of the Prelates, priests, and religious, who were forced to abandon their residences amidst atrocious outrages and threats of fire and death... (Episcopal Conferences of Colombia, 1956, pp. 464–465)

Certain sectors of the Church opposed the Archbishop of Bogotá, Ismael Perdomo, who considered that the clergy ought not to interfere by attacking Liberalism—unlike Monsignor Builes, who preached 'that being Liberal was a sin' and founded the Catholic weekly *El Derecho*, which in its April 1949 edition called on Conservatives throughout the country to take up arms.

Following the elections of 1950, Laureano Gómez, also of the Conservative Party, was declared president. In this climate, the National Government imposed difficulties in granting visas to Evangelical missionaries, while also imposing censorship on both Evangelical and secular radio and press programs.

The Catholic Church, which had apparently been waiting for just such an opportunity of social disorder, immediately launched a persistent campaign aimed at portraying the Protestant churches and groups as enemies of the government, subversive agents, and accomplices of rebels and guerrillas. Consequently, under cover of the political chaos, the most violent religious persecution that Evangelical Christians had suffered in recent decades was unleashed. (Ordoñez, 1958)

The Conservatives, calling for order and the faith of the Catholic Church, invented hymns that served as catalysts for hatred, bolstering Conservative morale and justifying abuses against Liberals and Evangelicals.

Francisco Ordoñez published the book *The History of the Evangelical Church in Colombia* in 1958, as a rebuttal to prior and contemporary Catholic defamatory campaigns, drawing on numerous testimonies from persecuted Evangelicals. According to him, the year 1948 demonstrated that political ambitions taken to an extreme plunged the country into an atmosphere of terror caused by the Colombians' deeply rooted cultural intolerance and the Catholic Church's manipulation of the masses. Similarly, Beltrán (2004) notes that pulpits were the most effective means of popular mobilization, and were used by priests to incite violence against institutions and figures who represented Liberal ideology—such as Evangelical pastors and reverends. Thus, the assassination of several Protestants was regarded as an act of defense of the Catholic faith.

Quintero (2012) compiles figures on attacks against Protestants in the country between 1948 and 1958, based on data provided by James Goff in *The Persecution of Protestant Christians in Colombia*. These figures document 1,869 cases of violence against persons, 537 acts of aggression against property, and 3,456 cases of non-violent persecution, which included the denial of individual rights, harassment, searches and confiscations, interference with religious practices, and persecution and discrimination against educational institutions and Protestant children. These hostilities may be compared with the Dreyfus Affair in France at the end of the nineteenth century, in which—due to the Jewish origin of Captain Alfred Dreyfus—he was expelled from the army and transferred to French Guiana on charges of treason. Anti-Semitism was the *casus belli* that resulted in protests embracing anticlerical and pro-republican ideas in that nation. In like manner, in Colombia, the violence perpetrated by the Catholic Church opened the eyes of many to demand the separation of Church and State and freedom of worship, echoing the calls for freedom of thought that the French Enlightenment had brought.

In this scenario of political-religious conflict, the Catholic Church had much to lose: if it did not support the Conservative Party, its authority would be threatened, losing faithful and capital, whereas Evangelical authority did not depend on such alignment. Correspondingly, Vasquez (2003) cites Professor Ricardo Arias, who states that the Catholic Church provided unconditional support to the elites while showing little interest in social problems.

According to Gaitán (2016), the abstention from attacks on the clergy by insurgents in several municipalities demonstrated a manifestation of the Church's longstanding historical domination. Starting in 1950, violence grew in the region, imposing an order of Liberal contempt, so that those arrested for holding these ideologies were executed—despite being told by authorities that they would be sent to departmental prisons. The only escape from this fate was silence and the denial of one's faith.

During La Violencia, many foreigners found themselves fighting a war that was not theirs—a religious war that depended on their love of God—giving little thought to their own lives so long as they could spread the Gospel. In the book *Hacaritama*, the couple Elof and Isabel Anderson—missionaries in Norte de Santander—recount their work. The couple arrived in 1937, during the Liberal Hegemony, but were subsequently struck by the retrograde Conservative ideas.

Through the intimidation of the priest, aided by local authorities, the majority (of missionaries) escaped to Venezuela and Cúcuta. The church building suffered great damage, and the local police oversaw the demolition [...] In this place the priest has erected a large statue of the Virgin. Doña María de Díaz, an eighty-three-year-old Christian woman, lives nearby [...] Two weeks ago the police gave her an ultimatum: She must attend Mass! (April 26, 1950; Anderson, E., 1977, p. 107)

While we were passing by the Río de Oro, five miles from Ocaña, we were stopped by the police. They asked for my papers and searched my luggage. When they discovered my Bible, hymnbook, and other Evangelical literature, they became enraged and immediately threatened me. They called me a Communist, an enemy of the people, and heaped insults upon me [...] They took me to police headquarters. Two officers were waiting for me. One of them immediately began to beat me with his fists. I protested [...] and so the officer drew his weapon and threatened to shoot me. He put me in a dark cell covered in human excrement. Then he threw me to the floor and kicked me mercilessly. (March 24, 1953. Anderson, E.)

Arboleda (2011) cites the Jesuit priest Eduardo Ospina, who attributed the main cause of anti-Protestant violence to their political interference: 'If they were not Liberals, there would be no political hostilities.'

Ordoñez also compiles harrowing testimonies of anti-Protestant violence in the country, including the following:

They assaulted the home of Aureliano Benavides, a Protestant believer who had been murdered the previous year, and attacked the widow with bullets and machetes; they then dismembered her in the presence of her son, whom they also left severely injured. A laborer who was lodged at the house that night was likewise wounded. They then doused him in gasoline and set him alight, but he managed to survive and was treated at the Maranatha clinic in Palmira. (Ordoñez, F., 1957, p. 154)

The mob was already breaking down the door. The two men hid under the beds while the children remained seated on the edges [...] the mob entered displaying their weapons and shouting: 'Long live Christ the King! Long live the Virgin of Carmen! Down with the Protestants!' There were 18 masked men armed with shotguns, revolvers, and machetes. The criminals tried to force the woman and children to shout the same [...] But they did not. They then asked where the men were and, suspecting they were hiding, began to strip the beds and dragged the two brothers out by force, pointing revolvers at their chests. Doña Ana begged them weeping not to kill them, that her husband was the father of nine children. The children were also crying in horror, but the hearts of those brutes were not softened by the heartrending scene, and they fired...they delivered several machete blows and stab wounds to the back and chest [...] The criminals then completely looted the house [...] the authorities would not permit the poor woman to be in charge of burying the bodies and threatened to 'shoot her if she kept causing trouble.' Señora Ana concludes her sorrowful account by saying: 'One of my children, Germancito, kept asking at every moment for his father, and shortly after died as the victim of a nervous breakdown caused by the events.' (Ordoñez, F., 1957, pp. 162–163)

According to López (2011), international newspapers such as The New York Times published the complaints of Evangelical missionaries against the government of Gustavo Rojas Pinilla—Colombian dictator from 1953 to 1957—and against the Catholic Church for engaging in a determined campaign of religious persecution in violation of Article 18 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which establishes freedom of worship.

V. Conclusion

The Bogotazo laid bare more than ever the tensions that had existed for decades between the Conservative and Liberal parties, as well as those allied with them in the pursuit of the political and monetary monopoly of Colombia. The disturbances unleashed a heightening of partisan violence, culminating in the destruction of Catholic sanctuaries and the deaths of priests primarily on April 9th, as well as a sustained and prolonged persecution of Protestants—a consequence of employing religion as a political battleground. The deaths of Catholics were attributable principally to the alignment of the upper echelons with the Conservative Party and its desire to perpetuate its supremacy, while the human and material losses of Evangelicals—far greater than those of Catholics due to the latter's majority and dominance in the territory—resulted from their mere desire to follow the Biblical teachings of spreading the Gospel and dying in defense of their faith.

The lack of critical thinking on the part of the masses was demonstrated, as several Catholic pulpits served as cruel promoters of anti-Evangelical and anti-Liberal ideas, linking them with socialism in the context of the Cold War and with Freemasonry, capitalizing on the ignorance of the masses—which they themselves had encouraged through their control over education, as before the Lutheran Reformation. The hypocrisy of certain figures within the Catholic Church was thus made evident in light of the principles of love and justice that it professes, as was its disobedience of the separation of Church and State mandated by the Constitution—violating as well the first-generation rights of many individuals without any subsequent judicial proceedings.

The investigation demonstrated how Colombia's history has been shaped by the role of violence, as a people softened under the guise of tradition and fear of authority, in need of a change only made possible through education. The limitations of this monograph lay in the scarcity of official

documents concerning Protestants—a minority religion marginalized in the country due to the aforementioned hatreds—as well as in the absence of judicial proceedings against the perpetrators. Nevertheless, it was a significant achievement to recover some of these testimonies and to become aware of the presence of the faith to which I belong in this country, as I had previously taken it for granted without considering the sacrifices that had to occur for me to know the love of God and practice my faith freely. This work may serve as a basis for future research on religious minorities in the country, and as a testament to attacks on Christians worldwide due to ideological differences and ignorance.

VI. References

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